

Challenges of Leadership in Virtual Teams

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2020

P-ISSN: 2321-4643

Impact Factor: 3.122

Citation:

Savitri Jayant, G.
“Challenges of
Leadership in Virtual
Teams.” *Shanlax
International Journal of
Management*, vol. 7,
no. S1, 2020,
pp. 159–61.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.3737752](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3737752)

Abstract

Technological innovations in information and communication have changed all aspects of our lives at a rapid pace. These changes provide an opportunity for organizations to employ talent from all over the world in work teams. Globalization has led to more complex and dynamic jobs and forced managers to lead organizations that consist of geographically dispersed business operations. Virtual teams are groups of geographically and/or organizationally dispersed coworkers that are assembled using a combination of telecommunications and information technologies to accomplish an organizational task. Leadership in virtual teams, generally referred to as e-leadership, has recently received a great deal of attention. E-leaders usually face several challenges that requires certain new skills in leading virtual teams when compared to conventional teams.

Introduction

Leadership in organizations remains a complex issue that generates plenty of interest and discussion. Leadership is the ability to inspire confidence and support among people who are needed to achieve organisational goals. Leadership is needed at all levels in an organization. The ability to influence and lead others effectively is a rare quality. Leadership requires voluntary cooperation and teamwork by means of influence and persuasion. Effective leadership will lead to organizational transformation for the better.

Virtual Teams

The team approach to managing organisations is having a diverse and critical impact on organisations and individuals. Teams prove to be cornerstones of progressive management of the future. Virtual teams are formed with members who are not collectively present physically in one place or space or location. Virtual teams operate independently of organizational boundaries, geographical locations, and time zones while striving effectively to reach the team-specific goals. The virtual team members who are globally scattered are basically linked through modern state of art information and communications technology which helps them to provide innovative and diversified business solutions to current smart sizes and lean business structures.

Leadership in Virtual Teams

Leadership in virtual teams setup is referred to as e-leadership, a new phenomenon of leadership. The term E-leadership is coined to reflect the new working environment where the team members interactions are channelled by information and communication technology, and where leaders may lead entire projects and its associated members from a distance or a remote location. E-leadership is primarily a response and solution to global changes resulting from technological advancements. It is widely accepted that e-leadership differs from conventional way of perceiving and understanding leadership as well as leadership forms practiced in traditional teams where leadership is based on one to one interactions. E-leaders can lead their virtual teams without ever physically meeting their team members. Such leaders may lead virtual teams working in the same space but at different times, or in different spaces and time lines where generally most, if not all, the interactions among team members take place through electronic communication network channels.

E- Leadership Challenges

Developing a virtual team is a challenging task for many organizations. Numerous studies exist about how organizations fail in developing virtual teams. In the process of developing virtual teams, e-leaders usually face some challenges since they only rely on technology largely for their communications and exchange of information and data. Let us now discuss those various challenges of E-Leaders.

1. **Interpersonal Trust:** Mutual trust plays a key role in successful and effective teams. Trust is based on the belief that team members are dependable in living upto the team expectations by delivering what they are expected to deliver in terms of their roles, duties and functions. Building trust in each other's skills, knowledge, abilities and efforts too is essential, yet challenging.
2. **Communication:** Effective and free flow of communication is fundamental to any organisations success, as it provides the basic network for people to collaborate, make decisions, and perform to achieve organizational objectives. Communication in virtual teams differ from face-to-face communication, because in virtual teams communication is typically based on technology mediated information and knowledge dissemination which allows multiple themes of conversation to occur simultaneously from multiple contributors from multiple locales. This can lead to miscommunication or communication bottlenecks, which can be caused due to technical snags.
3. **Lack of Proximity:** Distance is primarily considered to be one of the critical challenges e-leaders face while managing widespread team members, which often results in hidden costs in terms of time lost due to travel and also travel expenses. Time-related challenges arise significantly from the geographical distances meaning that the team members are fundamentally working in different time zones without overlapping work hours and so, the different time zones makes it very difficult for simultaneous work. Therefore, e-leaders face severe problems when coordinating tasks with the team members.
4. **Diversity and Inclusion:** Diversity can be understood as mutual acceptance and value placed on differences among team members with regard to age, class, ethnicity ability, race, sexuality etc. These differences may result in alienation of team members, posing as a challenge to e-leaders
5. **Team Cohesiveness:** It is the degree to which team members are attracted to and share a bonding among themselves as teammates. Lack of cohesiveness among team members greatly affects team performance, therefore e-leaders must design explicit activities to promote team building, and respond to diversified competing demands, address ambiguity of remote communication, and establish personal relationships with different team members.

6. **Language Differences:** when team members do not speak the same language, communication becomes slow and inefficient.
7. **Risks Associated with Location:** challenges that arise when the project is executed in a place where security is a concern. There are also problems that arise because of the lack of understanding of local laws.
8. **Ethics and Values:** Differences in ethical standards and values will bring about a difference in the attitude towards work. In some countries , bribery and corruption have become institutionalised, and undue preference may be given to local suppliers or contractors and planning laws and approval can be very bureaucratic.

Conclusion

Analysing the current available literature on leadership in virtual teams, demonstrates that virtual team members and leaders face unique challenges within a virtual team environment when compared to the conventional teams. It was found that there is a striking similarity and relationship between the problems of forming and developing virtual teams and the challenges that e-leaders face in managing virtual teams. Building trust, setting up of effective communication networks, cultural diversity and complexities in exchanging data and information are identified as some of the key challenges faced by e-leaders.

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